

Journey from Odisha to Uttarakhand

(a trend to change in floral diversity)

-By APRF Team

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From Odisha to Uttarakhand via West Bengal

The team of APRF head on from Odisha to Uttarakhand via West Bengal. The plan for the tour was not well planned as most of the unit funding for the organization are mostly used for the maintenance of the organization and survey works for documentation and awareness of the importance of Medicinal plants and conservation of biodiversity.

The team headed with the strong faith in God and with the strong intuition that the tour would be successful to observe the trend in variation of culture, rituals, vegetation, climate, etc.

The variation in the landscape and vegetation is huge as the landscape of Odisha starts from the coastal region of 0 m elevation above the Mean Sea Level to the high altitude of around 7,816 m elevation above the Mean Sea Level. However, the tour could cover up to the altitude of about 3000 m elevation.

The change in the landscape not only brings the variation in floral diversity but also the change in the culture, people, rituals, etc. as it passes from east to north. West Bengal is also located in the eastern part of the country with the varying landscapes viz. The Gangetic plains, the sub-Himalayan region and the Himalayan mountain ranges.

Coastal region of Odisha

The hills of Uttarakhand

The majority part of the state is mountainous with the youngest Himalayan Mountain System. The state having a unique biological diversity. It is also known as the Land of Gods or Devbhumi as it has many pilgrimages and many Hindu temples.

The mountain ranges of Uttarakhand

About Odisha

Odisha is a state known for its culture, heritage, history and natural resources, situated on the east coast of our country. It is the 8th largest state by area and the 11th largest by population. The State is drained by a number of important rivers, which includes Mahanadi (largest river of Odisha), Brahmani, Baitarni etc. The state has 30 districts, among which 12 are tribal districts. These tribes are mostly tagged to the districts namely Mayurbhanj, Keonjhar, Jajpur, Balasore, Bhadrak, Deogarh, Dhenkanal, Angul, Jharsuguda, Sundargarh, Kandhamal and more. While the Kondh and Santal tribes are the most widespread in Odisha, other tribes like Munda, Oram, and Gond also have a major impact on the state. Odisha's forests are well stocked; diverse, multi-storied and dense enjoys tropical monsoon type of climate. The State is also very rich in mineral resources. As per the Champion & Seth Classification of Forest Types (1968), the forests in Odisha belong to four Forest Type groups namely- Tropical Semi Evergreen, Tropical Moist Deciduous, Tropical Dry Deciduous, and Littoral and Swamp Forests, which are further divided into 19 Forest Types. Most common plant species found in Odisha are *Mangifera indica*, *Shorea robusta*, *Madhuca longifolia*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Anacardium occidentale* etc.

People live in Odisha are very simple and believe in Jagannath culture. Puri, the famous seat of Lord Jagannatha, is not only famous as the holy place of India but its surrounding is also treated as grand and splendid in the whole of world, popularly known as “Jagannath Dham” or “Srikhetra” or “Purusottam Dham”. Odisha is like a lotus in the lake of Bharatavarsha and the site of Jagannatha temple is the heart of the flower. The Jagannath cult and culture has encouraged the whole world

to be bound on world brotherhood giving up separatist ideas. The car festival of Lord Jagannath has spread the message of love for one and all besides encouraging one to resort to brotherhood amongst all. Culture of Lord Jagannath has affected unity in diversity by faith, and integrated human society with the help of human value.

People of Odisha mainly survive on agriculture. The major crops are rice, pulses, oil seeds, jute, coconut and turmeric. The crops like tea, cotton, groundnut and rubber are of great economic importance in other parts. Odisha contributes one tenth of the total rice produced in the country. Tribes of Odisha also depend on agriculture, fishing, farming, hunting and gathering of Non-Timer Forest Produces (NTFPs) like mahua, sal leaves, mushrooms, medicinal plants etc.

Some of the famous National parks in Odisha are Chandaka Elephant Reserve, Nandankan National park and Similipal National Park. Similipal Tiger Reserve was declared as a tiger reserve in the year 1956. It was given the grade of National Park in the year 1979. The most famous hill stations of Odisha are Taptapani, Mahendragiri, Olasuni and Dumuriput. Chilika Lake, the largest brackish water lagoons of the world are located on the east coast of the state.

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About West Bengal

West Bengal is located in the eastern part of the country. It is bounded to the north by the state of Sikkim, to the northeast by the state of Assam, to the east by the country of Bangladesh, to the south by the Bay of Bengal, to the southwest by the state of Odisha, to the west by the states of Jharkhand and Bihar, and to the northwest by the country of Nepal. West Bengal contains tracts of very different physical features like alluvial plains of the Ganges together with its deltas and a small portion of the sub-Himalayan region which form the main part of Darjeeling district. The network of river Ganges provides the state with the most striking feature. The Ganges is known as Padma from south of the point where the Bhagirathi leaves it. Along the northern part of Bengal numerous rivers move out of the Himalayas. On its right bank, the Ganges receives the Bhagirathi, which in the latter part of its course is called the Hooghly.

The vegetation cover of the state is around 27% of the geographical area. The vegetation cover includes village orchards / groves, tea garden and horticulture plantations. Forests occupy more than one-tenth of the total land area of the state, and the region as a whole has a rich and varied plant life. In the sub-Himalayan plains, the principal forest trees include sal (*Shorea robusta*) and Sissoo (*Dalbergia sissoo*); the forests are interspersed with reeds and tall grasses. The southern part of West Bengal can be divided into two regions: the Gangetic plain and littoral mangrove forests of the Sundarbans. The alluvial soil of the Gangetic plain, combined with favourable rainfall, makes the region especially fertile. The Western part of the state has similar vegetation with Chota

Nagpur Plateau. The coastal vegetation shows a predominant tree that is *Casuarina*.

Sundarbans is a mangrove area in the delta formed by the confluence of Ganges, Brahmaputra and Meghna Rivers at the mouth of Bay of Bengal in Bangladesh. A notable tree from the Sundarbans is the ubiquitous Sundari (*Heritiera fomes*), from which the forest gets its name. The forests of the state are inhabited by diverse animals like tigers, leopards, elephants, wild cattle and rhinoceroses as well as by other animals of the Indian plain, large and small. Reptiles and birds include the same species as are common throughout the Indian subcontinent.

Darjeeling is a beautiful town in West Bengal state, in the Himalayan foothills, a popular place to visit. Environmental conditions play a major role in conditioning the livelihood and economy of the people in Darjeeling; subsistence agriculture, livestock, forestry, plantations and allied activities are the major activity of the rural folks.

Bengal was the richest part of Medieval India, West Bengal has a long tradition of popular literature, music and drama largely based on Bengali folklore and Hindu epics and Puranas. Durga puja is the biggest festival in Bengal and is the most vibrant festival throughout the state.

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About Uttarakhand

Uttarakhand is a state in the northern part of India. It is often referred to as the Devbhumi due to the numerous Hindu temples and pilgrimage centres found throughout the state. Uttarakhand is known for its natural beauty of the Himalayas, the Bhabhar and the Terai. It is a beautiful place that is also called the land of lakes and waterfalls. It is a place where one can find some of the most beautiful landscapes, mountains, etc. The state is divided into two divisions, Garhwal and Kumaon, with a total of 13 districts. The state is rich in natural resources. The famous Himalayan peaks of Nanda Devi, Kedarnath, Badrinath, Trishul, Bandarpunch and Mt Kamet and the important glaciers like Gangotri, Pindari, Milam and Khatling are situated in this state. The Ganga, the Yamuna, Ramganga and Sharda are rivers contributing to the geography of this region. The Ganga and the Yamuna have their sources in this state and comprise the most famous and major rivers of the country as a whole.

People of this state are divided into regions recognized as Kumaoni and Garhwali. Apart from these two major inhabitants, Uttarakhand is also home to ethnic groups like Bhotias, Jaunsaries, Tharus, Bokshas, and Rajis. Like their simple lifestyle, the festivals and fairs in Uttarakhand are also simple yet culturally rich. Each season is welcome with hearty folk songs and dance and so are the agricultural periods. Garhwali is the main language spoken here.

Uttarakhand is rich in forest resources. The forests in Uttarakhand belong to nine Forest Type Groups, which are further divided into 43 Forest Types. Physiographically, the State can be divided into three zones namely, the Himalayas, the Shiwalik and the Terai region. The rural

people are largely dependent on them for their livelihoods and they have traditional practices to conserve forests. Uttarakhand lies on the south slope of Himalaya ranges and the climate varies from sub-tropical forests at lower elevation to glaciers at higher elevation. The altitude in the state varies from 200 to 7817 metre above mean sea level. The highest elevations are covered by ice and snow.

Forests provide fodder, fuel wood, many wild foods and medicines for humans and cattle. Besides these forests also create microclimate for cultivation of several crops of the hill. Thus, forests and their produce provide substantial livelihood for forest fringe areas. Non wood forest products (NWFPs) mainly medicinal plants and bamboos are gaining importance in bringing better livelihood opportunities. Agriculture is one of the most significant sectors of the economy of Uttarakhand. Basmati rice, wheat, soybeans, groundnuts, coarse cereals, pulses and oil seeds are the most widely grown crops. Fruits like apples, oranges, pears, peaches, litchis and plums are widely grown in this state.

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The Journey Begins

The journey started one winter morning in December with a clear sky. It started from Bhubaneswar or the “city of temples”, headed towards the north east to Kolkata, West Bengal. The journey was a pleasant one with warm winter sunlight beaming and reflecting the green fields and pastures. The bright yellow patches of *Brassica* spp. over a large area attracts the sight of the travellers. It crosses different rivers during its journey viz. the Mahanadi river, the Brahmini river, the Subarnarekha river and the Hooghly river. The team then headed to Nabadwip which is about 104 km by train. Nabadwip is known as a heritage town in the Nadia district of West Bengal. This town is a famous holy place and a birth place of Chaitanya Mahaprabhu, a great Vaishnava saint. This place is also an important pilgrimage for all the Vaishnava worldwide. The holy places of the Nabadwip Dham enchanted the place. The team experience the good opportunity to get to have local indigenous food as Prasadam or the food taken with the blessing of God. The journey then headed towards the north to the state Uttarakhand. The team experience different views and landscapes in this journey. In this journey, various rivers had been passed across the Hooghly river, along the Damodar river, across Kiul river, across the Ganges river, the Sone river, etc. In the course of this journey, various vegetation, landscape, avifauna, and cultivation of different crops have been observed. Plantation near railway lines of tree like *Dalbergia sisoo*, *Gmelina arborea*, *Eucalyptus* spp., etc. were observed. Patches of *Phoenix* spp. were also observed. Long patches of growth of different *Ziziphus* spp. was found. Uncommon species of trees like *Fernandoa adenophylla* is also seen fruiting. Some parasitic plants like *Cuscuta reflexa* was also noted. It was indeed

curious to find in some areas between Lucknow and Bareilly, there were no invasive plants like *Mikania micrantha* and *Lantana camara*.

In faunal species, spotted deer was spotted on this journey. Again, avifaunal species like Sarus Crane was spotted on a group of 7-8 and Peacock was also observed in the course of the journey. After a halt in Haridwar, one of the most important holy places in Uttarkhand, the team headed for Rishikesh and Auli. As there was a gradual increase in the height, the vegetation showed a great variation along with the drop of temperature. The team could cover up to the height of about 3000 m above sea level.

Haridwar

Nabadwip

The Change in Vegetation

We started our journey from Odisha, the cultural and beautiful state of India. Odisha's unique geographical location and diversity of physical characteristics like great range of mountainous woods, several tall peaks, long stretch of coast line, superb river rain system, brackish waterways, and coastal plains have combined to provide a rich and broad spectrum of vegetation with a variety of biological niches, result in a diverse floristic composition.

During the journey from Odisha to West Bengal we found many water bodies rich with diverse wetland floras. We have observed some carnivorous plants like *Utricularia* spp., along with that we found *Ipomoea carnea*, *Ipomea aquatica*, *Sida* spp. etc. also we have observed some common medicinal plants like *Areva lanata*, *Amaranthus* spp., *Solanum* spp. etc. There we observed some threats to the local flora like over spreading of two invasive spp. Water hyacinth (*Pontederia crassipes*) and *Mikania micrantha*. However, the general vegetation of West Bengal shows a diverse topography, consisting of high peaks of Himalaya in the northern extremes to coastal regions down south, with regions such as plateau and Ganges delta intervening in between. West Bengal is the only State in India where Himalayas are in the north and Sea is at the south, with both plains and plateaus covering the remaining region.

From West Bengal we entered the state Jharkhand, biodiversity rich states of India because of its origin, diverse physiographic and climatic conditions. The state lies on the Chota Nagpur plateau. It is well known due to its tribal populations, mineral resources, and its vast forest resources. Jharkhand is home to tropical moist deciduous and tropical

dry deciduous forests and the dominant plant species like *Shorea robusta*, *Diospyros melanoxylon*, *Pterocarpus marsupium*, *Gloriosa superba*, *Butea monosperma*, *Madhuca longifolia* etc. Here we observed undulating tracts, hills, valleys and ridges and consists primarily of crystalline rocks with different types of soil.

After that when we entered in Bihar and we found a fertile alluvial plain, occupying the Gangetic Valley. The natural vegetation of Bihar is deciduous forest, but only a small portion of the total area is forested. Most forests occur in the Himalayan foothills; those on the plain have largely been removed in order to cultivate the land. Commonly seen plants are like *Holarrhena antidysenterica*, *Bauhinia vahlii*, *Butea monosperma*, *Ziziphus* spp.

From Bihar, we move towards Uttar Pradesh. In this state only a few patches of natural forest are now found scattered here and there in the plains. Tropical Dry Deciduous Forests are found in all parts of the plains and the most common trees which are found in these forests are Safed siris (*Albizzia procera*), Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Gular (*Ficus glomerata*), Pakar (*Ficus infectogria*), Shishsam (*Dalbergia sissoo*) etc. We observed *Mikania micrantha*, *Parthenium hysterophorus* and *Lantana camara* was observed till Lucknow but after Lucknow, rarely seen *Mikania micrantha*.

Finally, we reached at our destination, the mountainous state of India, Uttarakhand, with highly varied topography, with snow-covered peaks, glaciers, deep canyons, roaring streams and beautiful lakes. The state includes alpine meadows in the extreme north, temperate forests in the Great Himalayas, tropical deciduous forests in the Lesser Himalayas, and thorn forests in the Siwalik Range and in parts of the

Tarai. Common tree species of the temperate forests include Himalayan cedar, Himalayan (blue) pine, oak, silver fir, spruce, chestnut, elm, poplar, birch, yew, cypress and rhododendron. Tropical deciduous forests of sal, teak, and shisham occur in the sub-montane tract. Here we found flora like *Polygonum capitatum*, *Nicandra physalodes*, *Trifolium repens*, *Strobilanthes wallichii*, *Cynoglossum lanceolatum*, *Lindenbergia grandiflora* etc.

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The Experience

We started our journey for documentation, awareness program and discussion on different aspects of medicinal plants from Odisha to Uttarakhand and we have to cover about 5000 km. We observed many medicinal plants in railway yard. We enumerated lot of medicinal plants in yard and near railway line. Most of observed species having medicinal values were *Butea monosperma*, *Pennisetum pedicellatum*, *Tridax procumbens*, *Hyptis* spp., *Ziziphus* spp., *Justicia adhatoda*, *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Gmelina arborea*, *Saccharum spontaneum*, *Phragmites* spp., *Haplophragma adenophyllum*, *Diospyros* spp., *Phoenix* spp. etc. Tadi, a country liquor is observed today which is used in Jaundice. We also observed the cultivation of Papaya, Marigold, vegetables etc.

Temple near Hooghly river

We ate many delicious and healthy foods like rice with *Ocimum* and little raw turmeric along with curry leaves, full of antioxidant agents.

Amla

Such food is able to increase immunity and can fight against disease & disorders. Hence, we have to have our traditional foods.

We have also covered about twenty sacred groves. Almost all sacred groves has Banyan tree (*Ficus benghalensis*), Pipal tree (*Ficus religiosa*), Jack Fruit (*Artocarpus*

heterophyllus), *Ocimum* spp, *Saraca asoca*, *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*, curry leaves (*Murraya koenigii*) etc.

We have tasted one product of Amla (*Phyllanthus emblica*). Raw fruit parts can get from market & tourist places at Mayapur & Nabadwip, West Bengal, India. It is good for digestion and many more. It is a traditional wild edible fruit, people used to have after meals. We have to purchase them so it will be available as a local food for future generation.

Slowly we forgot the earthen cup and using plastic and paper cup. We can't compare earthen cup to any other for taking tea. We should avoid the plastic and have to ask earthen cup only. Best for environment and also tasty. At Haridwar we also discussed with locals on medicinal plants and also with sellers. We enjoyed the local food including the boil fruits of *Trapa natans* (Pani singhda). It's a good local nutraceutical.

We also found *Opuntia dillenii* or Ramphal. This fruit is being sold by a roadside vendor. They cut the fruit in small pieces and served it with sugar and salt. According to the vendor this fruit having many medicinal

Ramphal

Pani singhda

properties, used to treat cancer, calcium deficiency, problem related to eye and also used for diabetes too. We observed lot of edible plants of

Local tubers, pulses and vegetables

Uttarakhand and documented them. Most common were *Anethum graveolens*, root of lotus, many nuts etc.

We enjoyed the beauty of Uttarakhand and their organic traditional food. Local communities grow lot of different pulses and used to sell them. They also consumed lot of tuberous plants including turmeric. Different types of plant species are documented. We also documented lot of plant species growing in minus degree and food of local cattle.

CONCLUSION

Travel always helps to enhance our lives and to gain experience as well. It creates a connection between people, place and culture. It exposes new things; new foods, culture, languages, traditions, vegetation, landscape and so forth. Documentation is needed to explore those experiences. This report enlightens the experiences of our journey from Odisha to Uttarakhand.

Recommendations, a scientific aspect

Cotoneaster microphyllus

Cynoglossum lanceolatum

Strobilanthes wallichii

Nicandra physalodes

Bidens pilosa

Nicotiana tabacum

Thalictrum spp.

Trifolium repens

Lindenbergia grandiflora

Justicia procumbens

Deeringia spp.

Persicaria capitata

Tagetes minuta

Urtica dioica

Crassocephalum crepidioides

Shri. Abali Lal (Arya)
 Uttarakhand Master Craftsman Award (2015 & 2016)
 (Uttarakhand State Shilp Khatna Award)
 Ringal Bamboo Master Craftsman

Parvatiya Ringal Hastshilp Udhog
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Promoting Uttarakhand Ringal Bamboo Art & Culture
 Reviving Traditional Art, New Designs with Natural Dyes & Handicrafts

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